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Situating Sanitation in the 21st Century Decoding the Problems, Paradoxes and Possibilities

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ABSTRACT

It is often argued, the quality of sanitation varies from nation to nation; within the same nation from state to state; within the same state from district to district; within the district from city to city, urban to rural areas and from village to village. A plethora of factors including the availability, accessibility, infrastructure, investment, awareness, costs, conditions, delivery, training and the like continue to impinge upon the politics and polemics of sanitation in regional, national and international levels. Sanitation is both a local and a global issue. Statistics is indeed intriguing. Needless to say, sanitation is not all about the provision of safe drinking water. Most of the agitations being witnessed globally relate directly or indirectly to the existing disparities, discriminations and deprivations faced by dwellers with regard to water and sanitation. Despite all-inclusive interventions at all levels, mankind is still struggling to ensure universal provision of safe drinking water to all. Based on select cases and insights from secondary sources, the present paper represents a critical endeavour to decode the conditions and challenges confronting sanitation and construct the roadmap ahead.

Key Words: Sanitation, Hygiene, Collective Consumption, Recycling and Reuse.

INTRODUCTION

As one goes through the literature on water and sanitation in national and global contexts, the information one comes across is baffling and bewildering. The UN in its 8th point in the SDG (Sustainable Development Goals) seeks provision for universalization of water and sanitation by 2030. Statistics reveals, around 163 million Indians are bereft of any access to safe water, which is the highest in the world. In India, about 31 per cent of the population has improved sanitation. Hand washing is only practiced by 53% of people after defecating and 38% prior to eating. As one observes the discourse of sanitation, the questions that haunt one's imagination are quite intriguing.

The UN states that having access to clean drinking water is a fundamental human right. Its goals are to: end open

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defecation; improve water quality by lowering pollution and minimizing the release of hazardous materials and chemicals; expand international cooperation regarding water harvesting, desalination, water efficiency, waste water treatment, recycling, and reuse technologies; and involve local communities in bettering water and sanitation management by 2030. All of these goals are to be reached fairly and affordably.

Sanitation: A Global Crisis

Evidently, the issue of sanitation is a global crisis not a mere Indian crisis alone. In Pakistan, some 50 million people lack access to clean drinking water, and only 42% of the population has access to sanitary facilities; of these, 65% live in urban areas and 30% in rural regions. (Zahid 2018). In underdeveloped and emerging nations, the mortality and morbidity rates are higher as a result of inadequate sanitation and drinking water.

About 4% of illnesses stem from poor sanitation, water and hygiene; around 2.2 million people die every year due to diarrheal illness globally (Zahid 2018). 771 million people across the globe live without access to safe water. 1.7 billion people live without improved sanitation.

The website *waterforpeople.org* reveals the following facts.

- Access to safe water is a problem for two billion people.
- The number of people who lack a good toilet is 3.5 billion.
- A quarter of the population lacks access to clean drinking water.
- Approximately 20% of individuals lack access to a clean restroom.
- Entire year, diseases associated to water cause 3.4 million fatalities.
- Nearly 90% of climate-related tragedies are linked to water.

The UNICEF website shares the following data,

- Only 69% of schools worldwide have access to clean drinking water.
- Almost half of the world's population lacks access to clean, safe sanitation.

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- There are three billion people who lack access to soap and water for hand washing.
- There are still 673 million people who defecate in open space.
- Every day, more than 700 children under five pass away from diarrheal illnesses as a result of inadequate access to sanitary facilities.

The UN facts reveal the following: approximately half of the population who do not have access to even the most basic form of drinking water reside in least developed countries, and eight out of ten of them reside in rural areas.

The statistics provided by the World Bank site is equally appalling, which is as follows.

- About 25% of people on the planet lack access to sanitary restrooms.
- Approximately 1.8 billion people lack access to safe restrooms or use hazardous toilets.
- The annual death toll from inadequate sanitation and hygiene is 1.6 million.

As per a study conducted in 2014, in Bihar, only 27% of homes have a toilet, and only 13% have a bathroom of their own. (Anderson, Kim. 2014).

Boland (2004) opines that around the world, several billions of people lack access to clean water, who do not have safe means of disposal of human waste; there are around one billion very people whose livelihood depends on adequate supply of water for irrigation. Further, as per statistics revealed by the WHO and UNICEF, the lowest percentage of any region in the world, just 30% of people in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) use improved private sanitation and hygiene facilities.

Needless to mention, sanitation is not exclusively about toilets. It encompasses a variety of things including access to water, safe drinking water, prevention of water-borne diseases, maintenance of hygiene of all kinds covering the menstrual ones, safe and clean disposal of human urine and faeces and the like. The existence of insufficient sanitation/ sewage or dumping facilities, people residing near open drains/ sewers in urban slums globally is not much surprising. The rural-urban disparities in access to tap water are found in almost all countries. These are not individual issues, rather collective issues; to conceptualize in the words of

Castells (1977), these are means of collective consumption, not individual consumption. To explain it in line with his arguments, most of the ongoing agitations/ protests and movements being witnessed globally relate to the existing discriminations, disparities and deprivations faced by the dwellers in the domain of water, sanitation and hygiene.

Not surprisingly, approximately half of girls attend schools without restrooms worldwide. (Rauch & Helgegren 2014.). Girls are more affected than boys in schools lacking proper toilets/ sanitary facilities. It is argued, when girls enter puberty, poor sanitation can make it more likely for them to drop out of school during their menstrual period. (WHO, 2009). As per UNICEF data, globally only 66% of schools have basic toilet services. Globally 600 million students don't have basic sanitation service at school.

Reasons Why Policy Guidelines and Prevailing Practices Conflict.

As one looks at the sanitation scenario and observes the disparities, it becomes very difficult to remain indifferent to the following queries. Can the government establish a sustainable future in which all people have simple access to potable, safe drinking water? Why does the actual progress in the sanitation domain remain sluggish despite all governmental interventions?

Government can't singularly bring changes overnight. Let me cite the situation in Rwanda. Despite enormous initiatives, there exists a huge gulf between policy targets and the grassroots reality owing to a number of reasons including the following. Toilets are not a top priority for people; household investment in toilets is limited by budgetary restrictions; awareness of recommended sanitation and hygiene rules and standards is low due to a lack of effort, and sanitary inspection methods are weak. The primary reason for the discrepancy between standards and practice is a lack of comprehension of how the system functions. People in Rwanda put low priority to and therefore invest minimum on toilets. It is forbidden to defecate inside or near residential areas. Toilets ought to be built outside the home's fence or far from the house. Most toilets are in poor condition. (Ekane Nelson et al. 2012). The reasons for slow progress also include the following.

- Insufficient investment.
- Inadequate coordination among line Departments/ agencies.

- Governance deficiencies.
- Poor political commitment.
- Poor leadership.
- Policies remaining on papers not translated in ground realities.

Nation to nation differs in the extent of progress made in urban and rural sanitation coverage. It must be realized, providing sanitation and water supply is not all about building infrastructure. It is also about addressing the deep-seated social, cultural, psychological and economic issues that impinge upon people's everyday approach to sanitation, service delivery and quality of lives. As Rauch and Helgegren (2014) point out, a caste of scavengers, for example, is responsible for handling human excreta in India. and the task itself is considered a polluting and degrading one; moreover, there is no visible drive to improve sanitation drive in this regard or to improve the life of the scavengers. Households with very low income find it extremely difficult to enhance their sanitation and water quality. In impoverished communities, the penetration of sanitation and piped water networks is remarkably low and as a part of their everyday coping strategies, people resort to open defecation and water vendors. Home access to clean water/ piped water is linked with social status, convenience and privacy. To put it in line with Douglas (1966)The ideas around contamination and purity frequently affect how people approach sanitation and how sanitation solutions are viewed and implemented. People's sanitation habits are to a great extent affected by cultural and religious traditions. It is a truism, water supply for households is typically the responsibility of women in many developing nations. They are constrained to go for open defecation/ public latrines, which in turn makes them more vulnerable to brutal assaults including rape. Under such circumstances, ensuring home access to water and sanitation implies a solid effort in empowering women too.

Sub-Saharan African (SSA) nations are making extremely slow and pitiful progress toward increased sanitation coverage, even in spite of massive foreign support. Approximately 70% of people in SSA still use open defecation and outdated shared sanitary facilities (Morella et al, 2008). The SSA countries are still grappling with a series of governance challenges including inadequate attention paid to sanitation, poor coordination and communication between stakeholders,

incongruence between water, hygiene and sanitation issues. The problems at the level of policy plaguing the sanitation sector in SSA are twin in number: dependency on external assistance and institutional inertia (Ekane Nelson et al. 2014).

Can external assistance result in adequacy in improvements in the sanitation sector? Experience from Ghana reveals, subsidy-based approach alone can't improve coverage or quality. More than 65% of urban households in Ghana reside in housings in which more than 3 households share a common toilet or are bereft of toilet facility (Dwumfour-Asare, Bismark et al. 2020).

Select Success Stories

Though disparities persist across the globe region-wise, citation of certain success stories will be educative. Experience suggests, it is possible to overcome the barriers and tackle the challenges in the path of ensuring the right to water for everyone. The scenario of Ethiopia is a case in point. As Sengupta and Anand (2020) report, the drive of sanitation has shown fast advances in the country called Ethiopia.

Ethiopia (Country Level): Strong political will, the understanding that sanitation is a health issue, the integration of drinking water and sanitation with the ministry of health, the active participation of local communities and political leaders, and the involvement of local communities in monitoring are all crucial factors in Ethiopia's success.

Sikkim (State Level): As far as anganwadi centers, schools, sanitary complexes, and rural and urban families are concerned, Sikkim is the first state in India to achieve 100% cleanliness. It is now a 100% open defecation free State in the country with the construction of 57525 household toilets, according to Swachh Bharat Mission data. Strong political and administrative will, strict legislation and its enforcement, the availability of resources, strong advocacy, and the participation of officials in awareness campaigns using booklets, pamphlets, documentaries, multimedia presentations, banners, posters, and billboards in both English and regional languages are some of the factors that made the State successful.

Taranagar (Block Level): Taranagar (Charu district, Rajasthan, India) exhibited spectacular success in the sanitation drive owing the strong and determined administrative will (resolute leadership of the district Collector); well-orchestrated and inclusive awareness

drive focusing on open defecation, malnutrition, health and related issues; paying respect to people's choice over the toilet types; easy availability of loans and incentives; capacity development programmes; effective monitoring and the like.

Tamana (Village Level): It is situated in the district of Ganjam, Odisha, India. Tamana village could witness metamorphic shift in the domain of sanitation owing to the strong will of the villagers to engineer change, involvement of NGOs, easy availability of funds, simplification of pipe water supply, effective monitoring and the like.

The experience emerging from success stories concerning various parts of the globe does not manifest itself as an attempt to hush up the darker side of the scenario. Nor is this an effort to over-exaggerate the accomplishments. Instead, it represents a modest endeavour to rise above the problems/ paradoxes and materialize the possibilities in a realistic manner. Such success stories tend to remind us of the assumption that the provision of sanitation services is attainable and universalizable. As Sengupta & Anand (2020) conclude, the following should be considered in any serious campaign to achieve complete sanitation or independence from open defecation: strong/credible political and administrative will, a decentralized, community-centric awareness and education program, a robust implementation strategy, and outcome-based monitoring.

Finite Propositions

A thorough observation of the sanitation discourse – local to the global – urges one to come out with the following finite propositions.

- The provision of sanitation services receives higher priority in urban areas than rural areas.
- It is more structured in urban areas than rural areas.
- Urban—rural divide exists in sanitation service delivery.
- Disparities do persist between urban and rural sanitation coverage.
- Taboos of numerous kinds including personal, ideological, cultural and religious abound in relation to sanitation preferences. Habits are not easy to change.

- Undoubtedly, the water/ drinking water crisis is not a mere rural issue.
- Collecting water still constitutes an everyday battle for millions including women worldwide.
- Many schools across the globe are yet to possess the much requisite/ essential sanitation provisions including toilets and changing rooms for girls to provide privacy during menstruation.
- The type of sanitation services, including their acceptance, availability, and coverage, differs from country to country; within a country, states to states; within a state, districts to districts; within a district, urban to rural areas; within a block, Panchayat to Panchayat; and within a Panchayat, villages to villages.
- Involvement of all including the government agencies, national and international bodies, corporate and the communities certainly contributes a lot to improve water quality, set up toilets, promote adoption of improved hygienic practices including access to safe drinking water, water conservation, rain water harvesting, manage human waste effectively, prevent water-borne diseases and the like.
- The state policies and flagship programmes do carry the much needed potential for attaining freedom from open defecation, ensuring universalization of safe drinking water, prevention of water-borne diseases, gender-friendly sanitation provisions in educational institutions and the like.

The Roadmap Ahead

Promoting the fundamental minimum sanitation/ hygiene standards and ensuring health, safety, and livelihood require a shared and comprehensive awareness of the sanitation policy guidelines and standards at all societal levels. As Ekane Nelson et al. (2014) based on their Rwanda experience aptly conclude, there will undoubtedly be a demand for sanitation and hygiene facilities regardless of cost if people have a clear knowledge of how important it is to have such facilities built and maintained. Due focus be laid on investment, construction of sanitation infrastructure, promotion of equitable and inclusive service delivery, management of sanitary waste, reuse and recycling of used water, engagement of trained sanitation professionals in sanitation work, creation of digital database and use of digital technology in

sanitation services etc (Vatanan 2024). The ultimate mission should be to guarantee reliable, affordable, accessible and safe sanitation services to all citizens thereby ensuring safe management of solid and liquid waste.

Laws, regulations, and incentives must be used to put effective policies into action. They should be universally comprehensible for effective dissemination, implementation and monitoring for 100% sanitation coverage. The prescription of Hutton (2012) is worth contemplating: the bottlenecks in scaling up sanitation services vary from case to case; therefore the corresponding interventions and solutions must be context and location-specific. Universalization of the provisions of water, sanitation and hygiene entails participation of all starting from the decision-making to implementation: the state machinery, industry, communities and the external non-government organizations. It's preposterous, unrealistic and over-ambitious to seek radical changes in geometric progression; this is part of an evolutionary march wherein the success can be engineered brick by brick.

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